

AIAL Feedback on Stakeholder Consultation on Revised National Digital and AI Strategy for Ireland

Date: 10th September 2025

Authors:

Harshvardhan J. Pandit, AI Accountability Lab (AIAL)

Nana Nwachukwu, AI Accountability Lab (AIAL)

Contributors:

Abeba Birhane (AIAL)

Cite as: Harshvardhan J. Pandit and Nana Nwachukwu (2025, September) "AIAL Feedback on Stakeholder Consultation on Revised National Digital and AI Strategy for Ireland" AI Accountability Lab (AIAL).

<https://aial.ie/research/policy/consultation-2025-IE-National-AI-Strategy>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17141314

Cite as: "AIAL Feedback on Stakeholder Consultation on Revised National Digital and AI Strategy for Ireland" (2025, September) Harshvardhan J. Pandit, Nana Nwachukwu DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17127738](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17127738). Url: <https://aial.ie/research/consultations-2025->

INTRODUCTION

This document represents the answers prepared by the team at AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) for the *AIAL Feedback on Stakeholder Consultation on Revised National Digital and AI Strategy for Ireland*, published by the Department of Taoiseach in the Government of Ireland. The consultation follows the earlier plan¹ to update the National Digital and AI Strategy in 2025. It was open for feedback until 10th September 2025, during which the AIAL team submitted its response.

ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and

1

<https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-the-taoiseach/press-releases/updated-national-digital-strategy-2025/>

disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets. We are also invested in conceptual and critical work that advances frameworks and theories of change that underpin algorithmic audit, model evaluation, and meaningful accountability. We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

Call for Feedback

The 2025 Programme for Government, *Securing Ireland's Future*, sets out a commitment to harness the digital and AI revolution to deliver effective and modern public services and to grow the economy. This includes a commitment to update the National Digital Strategy in 2025, to signal our strategic ambition on Digital and AI, commensurate with our aim of remaining a global digital leader.

Key digital commitments in the Programme for Government include:

- Investing to make Ireland a regulatory hub for companies operating across the EU Digital Single Market;
- Transforming our public services through applying the latest technologies and upskilling;
- Realising the full benefits of digitalisation, including AI, to increase productivity of Irish businesses, and ensure small businesses are supported to achieve basic digital intensity;
- Ensuring investment in, and provision of digital skills and literacy at all levels, including in AI and Quantum Computing;
- On digital infrastructure, continuing to deliver and drive the adoption of high speed, reliable, quality broadband and 5G, expansion of the Connected Hubs network, and recognising the central role data centres play in contributing to economic growth and the enterprise economy;
- Strengthening cyber security through a new National Cybersecurity Strategy and promoting a centre of excellence for cybersecurity skills;
- Resourcing and implementing the new EU Online Safety Framework to protect vulnerable groups from online harm, and help tackle disinformation;
- Implementing an eInclusion Strategy to ensure no one is left behind by the move to a digital society.

The current National Digital Strategy, *Harnessing Digital – The Digital Ireland Framework*, was published in February 2022. It includes a focus on the digitalisation of Enterprise, Infrastructure, Skills and Public Services, as well as ensuring a coherent, modern and fit-for-purpose digital regulatory framework, in recognition of Ireland’s central role in European digital regulation.

Harnessing Digital aligns with the EU Digital Decade 2030 Programme and related Digital Compass targets. Significant progress has been achieved to date, as set out in annual Progress Reports, and reflected in the European Commission’s annual State of the Digital Decade reports.

The National Digital Strategy will be updated over 2025 to set out Ireland’s vision for Digital and AI across government, to ensure continued growth and investment over the coming years. In addition to supporting the achievement of EU-level Digital Decade targets and related EU digital initiatives in the areas of Enterprise, Skills, Public Services, Infrastructure, Regulation and Cyber Security, the updated Strategy will also set more ambitious national targets in key areas, with a significant focus on AI throughout.

It will also align with and provide a high-level focus to related existing and forthcoming sectoral strategies across Government, including: National Strategy on Semiconductors; Action Plan for Competitiveness and Productivity; Technology Skills of the Future Roadmap; National Connectivity Strategy; Cybersecurity Strategy; Digital Public Services Plan 2025-30; Public Service Data Strategy; AI in Health Strategy; and National Counter Disinformation Strategy.

Feedback Submitted

Question 3:

What should Ireland’s overall vision for an updated Digital & AI Strategy to 2030 be?

Ireland's vision for the next decade should be focused on providing strong economic growth that is accompanied by societal wellbeing. For this, the strategy should establish not just short-term goals and principles, but also long-term vision and processes/action on the ground towards making it happen. In particular, the strategy should emphasise the non-optionality of Irish and European rights, freedoms, and values in digital technologies, particularly AI. This should be backed by a call for greater transparency and accountability as part of the strategy to guide and shape the direction of technological innovation and its impact on society. The strategy should promote such socially-responsible innovation at all levels – from third-level education to the environment to develop and sustain startups as

well as to control and temper the influence of large organisations in order to flourish new ideas and initiatives.

For this, the strategy should establish a plan to identify and execute robust accountability mechanisms and enforcement actions to both prevent harms as well as to swiftly investigate and adjudicate incidents when they occur. Finally, the strategy should be explicit about the current political reality which necessitates focus on development of "technical and economic sovereignty" where expertise is grown at grassroot levels rather than being dependent on big-tech, particularly through academic and research incentives. Unfortunately, this is no longer a hypothetical risk but an escalating reality. This makes sovereignty an essential action as without it Ireland will be reliant on external actors and organisations, who may import and promote political agenda and societal values that are incompatible with Irish and European norms.

Question 4:

In developing its domestic AI capabilities, what areas should Ireland focus on? Identify top 5 key AI actions/enablers the Government should prioritise to accelerate its AI ambitions.

While we are certain that other submissions to this consultation will provide sufficient feedback regarding technical innovation in relation to AI, in our submission we are focusing on the key principles outlined in our response regarding Ireland's strategy. In particular, we are concerned about auditing and consumer protection (broader: legal enforcement) as two key AI-related capabilities which should benefit from greater attention in the broader vision and planning such as this strategy. Auditing capabilities should be established outside of Big Tech support as any experts, technical know-how, or in-kind resources they provide would be conflicts of interest when regulating their activities – particularly as there is an immense risk of lobbying and capture, and also because these very entities are and continue to be subjects of legal violations with global attention on Ireland's practices regarding this. This is a great opportunity for Ireland to show how economic interests and political and corporate friendliness can be sustained and promoted without compromising on values and rights. Further, and more importantly, regulating AI activities by authorities will require in-house expertise which is severely lacking at the moment.

Second, establishment of robust liability procedures that are focused on human rights and freedoms is an urgent necessity in terms of capability development. Such knowledge and competency is necessary in order to make rights infringements a red line that must not be violated or toed in the name of AI progress or misdirections of its future harms. Similarly, capacity development should also focus on establishment and piloting of transparency, accountability, and principles-based (fairness, equity, justice) procedures for adoption of AI

in public services and institutions, in particular within the health, finance, and education sectors as these represent the key pillars of Irish society. Finally, the capacity to regulate should also be promoted – in particular by revitalising consumer protection at policy (law), enforcement (CCPC), and public (awareness) levels in order to safeguard consumers rights as AI-based hype increases and consumers are left unprotected and vulnerable to manipulation and extortion.

Question 5:

Please suggest 5 tangible priority actions the Strategy could include.

- 1) National framework for safeguarding fundamental rights and freedoms. This should act as a guideline for other agencies and departments to produce targeted plans for its execution.
- 2) Establish a mechanism for rapid detection, mitigation, and prevention of harms based on preventative action (e.g. requiring approval) – the above framework should call for this action to be implemented by all oversight and regulatory bodies with urgency.
- 3) Auditing of planned activities that occur at societal scale (e.g. through GDPR's DPIA and AI Act's notifying body) – especially regarding health and public services with transparency and assured competency.
- 4) Support services for organisations, especially SMEs to conduct and utilise fundamental rights impact assessments and auditing methodologies, as an economic booster without compromising on rights and freedoms
- 5) Setting up academic and research agendas to create expertise, particularly in third-level institutions to realise the above as part of public benefit and societal duties, and private bodies are compelled to prioritise innovation over rights protection.

Question 6:

Given Ireland's ambition as a European regulatory hub, and centre of excellence, what opportunities do you see to improve our digital regulatory framework?

The best mechanism for ensuring and directing the societal uptake of AI technologies is through legislation and robust enforcement. We therefore propose that the Irish legislative vision should include creating an "Accountability Act" that outlines the procedures and timelines to hold a body accountable when it misuses AI or causes harm. This single enforcement framework should also help authorities co-ordinate at national level rather than wade through enforcement setups individually defined in GDPR, AI Act, EHDS, etc. each of which has overlapping accountability mechanisms which will cause friction, delays, and increases in costs while delaying or failing to regulate urgent matters.

As a centre of excellence, such legislative principles and initiatives will also promote Ireland as a "stable" regulatory environment as the rules would have been set, as opposed to developing uncertainty and potentially changing rules in the future. Most importantly, because of the lack of such initiatives, this will be an excellent promotional opportunity to develop capacity within Ireland itself, and alongside European peers, thereby promoting Ireland as a world leader in terms of not only technical excellence but also its responsible regulation and its use towards societal wellbeing.

A short-term measure to support this include Sandboxes that prioritise auditing and enforcement challenges rather than merely being support tools for niche business cases. The purpose of sandboxes should be to learn how to regulate, and in the case of AI, it is vital to develop auditing capabilities and their translation into legal mechanisms for enforcement. We therefore also suggest setting up such mechanisms with public participation and taking onboard the available expertise in third-level research bodies in order to support aforementioned capacity building activities.

Question 7:

Please include any suggestions you have to ensure the strategy is inclusive and of value across society.

It is essential and vital that the strategy is explicit about involving participatory action (accompanied by research) as the best mechanism for inclusion of society. In this, the strategy should support and utilise CSOs and Universities as a balancing voice against private bodies. In particular, the strategy should certainly balance the call for greater innovation by facilitating technical expertise while also providing validity for stakeholders who warn against its risks and harms as both voices must be heard and respected in order to shape and direct AI and digital technologies responsibly. The national framework for safeguarding rights and freedoms is aligned with regulatory and governance obligations, such as Human Rights Impact Assessment before deployment of High-risk AI systems with public transparency, and an action plan on operationalising conformity assessments. These measures should provide avenues for the incorporation of diverse voices and concerns from societal stakeholders.

Question 8:

Any other relevant feedback/suggestions.

1. The strategy should emphasise how to predict, avoid, mitigate, and then litigate potential AI harms.

2. The strategy should ensure that harms investigations and mitigations require both ex-ante and ex-post audits that go beyond minimal legal documentation as the law is often severely lagging behind technical innovation.
3. It's a political reality that Ireland has the US BigTech benefit/burden, and that currently the political climate is adversarial to EU regulations. This should be an urgent call for sovereignty in technical expertise rather than relying on US tech to do our "homework" for us and then complaining it doesn't look right.
4. The strategy should prioritise research and capacity development in the national research agendas and in the regulatory / learning hubs so that this also promotes local research outcomes outside of corporate mechanisms, and more importantly helps achieve capacity development.
5. The strategy should also establish the need for oversight regarding governance of emerging technologies. For example, an AI Ombudsman which would have members of the academia & civil society in its advisory board. The Ombudsman will have the power to investigate public complaints about algorithmic decisions. It should be constituted in a way that it would act as a crucial advocate for Irish residents or users of Irish Government systems who feel they have been harmed or treated unfairly by an AI system.